

COARCTATION OF THE AORTA, FROM DIAGNOSIS TO PROBLEMS IN URGENCIES AND EMERGENCIES

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Introduction: Coarctation of the aorta is a congenital heart disease characterized by narrowing of the aorta, the main artery in the human body. This can lead to a series of severe clinical conditions, especially in cases of late diagnosis. As part of this disease, the heart needs to apply greater pressure when pumping blood through the narrowed aorta, which leads to an increase in blood pressure and a series of symptoms, such as headaches, fatigue, dyspnea and dizziness. In addition, coarctation of the aorta can lead to other serious complications, such as aortic aneurysms and ruptures. **Objective:** To analyze the importance of early diagnosis of coarctation of the aorta in order to reduce the aggravation of this condition in cardiac emergencies. **Methodology:** This is an integrative literature review, with a reflective, descriptive and qualitative analysis. We used 05 articles available in the Revista Latino-Americana de Enfermagem (Rev. Latino-am), Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) and Literatura Latino-Americana e do Caribe em Ciências da Saúde (Lilacs); from the crossing of the descriptors "Coarctation of the Aorta", "Diagnosis", "Emergency" being paired in boolean AND. **Results:** Early diagnosis of this congenital heart disease is essential to prevent the patient from developing cardiac emergencies in the future. Symptoms usually appear in childhood or adolescence, and a careful physical examination with pulmonary and cardiac inspection and auscultation, together with imaging tests such as chest X-ray and echocardiogram, can confirm the diagnosis. If coarctation of the aorta is left untreated, it can lead to serious cardiac emergencies such as heart failure, stroke and even sudden death. Treatment usually involves surgery or endovascular procedures to repair or bypass the narrowing of the aorta. **Final considerations:** In conclusion, coarctation of the aorta is a congenital heart disease that can lead to serious cardiac emergencies if there is no early diagnosis through physical examination and imaging. It is important for health professionals to be aware of the signs and symptoms of this condition and to have the appropriate semiotechnical skills to carry out the physical examination successfully.

Keywords: Congenital heart disease. Congenital. Care.

Thematic Area: Urgency and Emergency in Medicine, Nursing and Dentistry.